

IMPROVING DIGITAL MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING SYSTEMS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF PASTURE LAND USE

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada yaylov yerlaridan samarali foydalanishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Global oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, resurslar tanqisligi va iqlim o'zgarishi sharoitida yaylovlardan oqilona foydalanish chorvachilikni rivojlantirishda muhim omil sifatida ko'rsatib berilgan. Naslchilikni rivojlantirish, zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish, yem-xashak bazasini mustahkamlash orqali soha samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari asoslab berilgan. Yaylovlardan to'g'ri foydalanish iqtisodiy barqarorlik va aholi farovonligiga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: yaylov yerlar, samaradorlik, chorvachilik, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, resurslardan foydalanish, naslchilik, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В данной статье проанализировано социально-экономическое значение эффективного использования пастбищных угодий. В условиях глобальной продовольственной безопасности, нехватки ресурсов и изменения климата рациональное использование пастбищ определено как важный фактор развития животноводства. Обоснованы пути повышения эффективности отрасли за счет развития племенного дела, внедрения современных технологий и укрепления кормовой базы. Правильное использование пастбищ способствует экономической стабильности и повышению благосостояния населения.

Ключевые слова: Пастбище эффективность, животноводство, продовольственная безопасность, использование ресурсов, племенное дело, социально-экономическое развитие

Annatation. This article analyzes the socio-economic importance of the effective use of pasture lands. In the context of global food security, resource shortages, and climate change, rational use of pastures is identified as a key factor in the development of livestock farming. The paper substantiates ways to improve sector efficiency through breeding development, implementation of modern technologies, and strengthening of the fodder base. Proper use of pastures contributes to economic stability and public well-being.

Key words: pasture lands, efficiency, livestock farming, food security, resource utilization, animal breeding, socio-economic development

The global problems that plague the world today are increasing. One of the most rapidly globalizing problems in the 21st century is the increasing shortage of food and agricultural products in the world. The rapid growth of the world's population, the depletion of natural resources, and the sharp decline in soil fertility limit the effective use of pastures. According to the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), as a result of global climate change, the

increasing price of food products in the world and the inability to meet the needs of the population are causing problems in various sectors.

Taking into account the natural conditions of the regions and market demands, it is necessary to develop animal husbandry by integrating cattle breeding, sheep breeding, fishing, and beekeeping and radically reforming the sector. Therefore, the implementation of land and water reforms in the development of the livestock sector demonstrates the need for effective use of existing pastures. The introduction of a system of state socio-economic support for the use of pasture lands will allow the sector to further develop. The reforms currently underway in agriculture are a program for the development of the farming and livestock sector.

Farms specializing in breeding should also develop the provision of livestock to farm members on a lease basis for the purpose of production, in which contractors should be encouraged to increase the number of livestock, improve their breeds, increase their breeding, and produce more and more products, based on the services they provide and the amount of products they produce. In solving these issues, farms should implement measures to ensure the increased productivity of pasture lands and adapt lease relations in this regard to the requirements of the free market. It is time to pay special attention to the gradual development of the material and technical base of livestock farms that meets modern requirements.

It is necessary to ensure that livestock farming is provided with appropriate means, that livestock is well cared for, and that new techniques and advanced technologies are introduced to produce quality products. Only then will production processes in the sector be mechanized and labor productivity will increase.

Developing breeding work, creating pedigree livestock breeds and ensuring their rapid introduction into production, while not forgetting to use the option of purchasing purebred, pedigree livestock, will increase the chances of achieving the expected results. To strengthen the feed base of livestock farming, it is necessary to expand the areas under fodder crops and develop crop rotation. In this regard, special attention should be paid to the water supply of areas under fodder crops, improving the melioration condition, and using organic and mineral fertilizers at the required level.

To solve this problem, it is necessary to organize the purchase of nutritious feed produced at processing enterprises at the required level, and the timely provision of formulated feed to livestock on a ration basis. Taking into account the urgency of this issue, the government of the republic should introduce ways and mechanisms to provide economic assistance to farms. In particular, it will be possible to eliminate existing problems by allocating preferential loans for the development of food production, exempting them from customs payments if material and technical resources are imported from abroad for this purpose, and implementing other measures.

Therefore, along with the preservation of pastures, the preservation and processing of fodder products obtained from them remains an important task. This process, unlike the one carried out by farms operating in agriculture, is carried out by several enterprises separately. Therefore, in the implementation of each process, the organization and the farm are engaged only in fulfilling their own tasks. This, in turn, prevents the effective implementation of reforms in the sector and the use of effective methods for expanding pastures, which prevents the volume of harvested crops from increasing at a higher rate. Therefore, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-24 of February 16, 2023 "On additional measures to protect pastures and ensure their rational use" in the Republic of Uzbekistan sets out a number of

specific measures to protect pastures, ensure their rational use, as well as further develop pasture farming and implement the widespread use of resource-saving technologies in pastures.

The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZURQ-538 “On Pastures” dated May 20, 2019, granted the right to graze livestock and mow hay in accordance with measures for the use and protection of pasture lands; carry out work on the construction of pasture infrastructure; and establish associations of pasture users. At the same time, pasture users are obliged to:

- use pastures rationally for their intended purpose;
- take measures to promote the reproduction of pasture plants, restore vegetation cover, and prevent pasture degradation;
- organize and adhere to pasture rotation;
- take measures to prevent fires in pastures and ensure the timely elimination of fire outbreaks;
- implement measures to combat pests and diseases of pasture plants;
- comply with the established rules, norms and standards aimed at preserving pastures.

Measures for the use of pastures are drawn up based on the data of the inventory and geobotanical inspection of pastures and include:

- a list of pasture users;
 - a list of livestock intended for grazing on pastures;
 - prevention of animal diseases;
 - a map with the boundaries and areas of pastures;
 - a calendar table of seasonal herd movements, schemes of pasture rotation, places where livestock are driven and pastures used;
 - development of pasture infrastructure facilities, including the restoration of water bodies;
- The need to improve the condition and quality of pastures, prevent the degradation of pastures by enriching pastures with plants, and further expand the opportunities for increasing the income of business entities has been clearly identified.

At the heart of the ongoing economic reforms aimed at improving the condition of pastures, one of the most pressing issues is to provide the livestock sector with a feed base and fully satisfy the population's demand for quality food products, fill the market with high-quality, safe and affordable meat and dairy products, strengthen the purchasing power of the population, and liberalize foreign economic activity, further increase export potential, and develop a healthy competitive environment.

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